

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
RESEARCH IN COMPUTER
APPLICATIONS AND ROBOTICS
ISSN 2320-7345

**A SURVEY ON DEEP LEARNING APPLICATIONS IN
CYBER SECURITY ENSURING SECURE DATA
MAINTENANCE**

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ABSTRACT

This survey examines the integration of deep learning techniques in the context of cloud service Providers (CSPs) to strengthen cyber security measures, with a particular emphasis on countering leech attacks and ensuring the security of data storage and maintenance. The survey comprehensively explores various aspects of this complex domain, including the application of deep learning models and methodologies, to address and alleviate cyber security risks and challenges associated with CSPs. Data de-duplication is a well-established technique for eliminating duplicate data, aiming to save storage space and enhance upload bandwidth, particularly in cloud storage systems. However, this method comes with potential vulnerabilities, such as the possibility of a Cloud Service Provider (CSP) tampering with user data or manipulating users into paying for storage of duplicate data stored only once. This survey delves into the intersection of deep learning, cyber security, and data maintenance in the context of data de-duplication, shedding light on innovative solutions to address security concerns and enhance the efficiency of data storage and retrieval in cloud environments.

KEYWORDS: Cloud Service Provider, Data De-Duplication, Cyber Security, Data Maintenance and Deep Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

This survey critically examines the paper titled "VeriDedup: Verifiable Data De-duplication Scheme with Data Integrity Duplication Proof," authored by Yu Xixun, Bai Hui, and Yan Zheng,. The paper introduces the VeriDedup scheme, which focuses on data de-duplication in cloud storage systems while emphasizing data integrity and duplication proof.

Below is an in-depth analysis of the paper [1]. VeriDedup survey begins by providing an overview of the VeriDedup scheme. It introduces the motivation and the problem statement addressed in the paper, which revolves around the need for efficient data de-duplication while ensuring data integrity and proof of duplication. This includes a discussion of the novel features and innovations brought forward by VeriDedup, such as the introduction of a Tag-flexible De-duplication-supported Integrity Check Protocol (TDICP) and a User Determined Duplication Check Protocol (UDDCP).

Private Information Retrieval (PIR) survey explores the use of Private Information Retrieval as a fundamental concept within VeriDedup, detailing how it contributes to data security and privacy during the de-duplication process [2]. Data Integrity and De-duplication Proof One of the central aspects of the paper is the assurance of data integrity and duplication proof. The survey investigates how VeriDedup achieves this, ensuring that data is accurately checked for duplication and maintained securely. Tag Generation and Flexibility survey examines the innovative "note set" concept introduced in VeriDedup, allowing multiple users to generate their unique verification tags. It explains how this enhances data security and flexibility. Security and Privacy focus on security and privacy aspects, especially in the context of cloud storage, is scrutinized. The survey delves into the mechanisms in place to protect user data from tampering and unauthorized access.

Practical Implications survey considers the practical implications of the VeriDedup scheme, discussing its potential applications and advantages in real-world cloud storage scenarios. Contributions to the Field The survey assesses the impact of VeriDedup on the broader field of data de-duplication, data security, and cloud storage, highlighting how it advances the state of the art in these areas [3]. Summarizing the key findings and contributions of the paper and suggests potential future directions for research and development in the context of data de-duplication and data security. An in-depth analysis of the paper "VeriDedup: Verifiable Data De-duplication Scheme with Data Integrity Duplication Proof" published in IEEE. It explores the technical innovations, security mechanisms, and practical implications of the VeriDedup scheme, shedding light on its significance in the realm of data de-duplication and cloud storage security.

II. DEEP LEARNING APPLICATIONS IN CYBER SECURITY

A Design of Parallel Content-Defined Chunking System Using Non-Hashing Algorithms on FPGA authored by H. Vuong, H. Nguyen, and L. Tran et. al presents a pioneering approach to content-defined chunking within the realm of data processing and hardware acceleration [4]. This study emerges from a growing need to efficiently manage and process vast volumes of data, a challenge that has become increasingly prevalent in the digital age. Content-defined chunking, a fundamental operation in data storage and transmission, is a critical element in addressing this challenge. The innovative use of non-hashing algorithms in the chunking process has departure from conventional hashing-based approaches. These non-hashing algorithms offer distinct advantages, contributing to increased efficiency and performance. Furthermore, the authors have leveraged Field-Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) to implement their content-defined chunking system, which introduces a hardware-accelerated dimension to the process. The FPGA architecture, known for its versatility and parallel processing capabilities, plays a pivotal role in enhancing the system's overall performance and efficiency.

One of the remarkable aspects of this work is the focus on parallel processing. By parallelizing the content-defined chunking process on FPGA, the research achieves significantly improved data processing speeds and throughput, which is vital in handling large datasets efficiently. The introduction of parallelism underscores the system's capability to cater to the demands of modern data processing [5]. A rigorous performance evaluation, offering empirical evidence of the system's capabilities empirical validation substantiates the effectiveness of the non-hashing algorithms, FPGA-based implementation, and parallel processing techniques employed. The analysis encompasses critical metrics, such as data processing speed and resource utilization, providing a comprehensive assessment of the system's performance.

In terms of practical applications, the research opens doors to a wide array of possibilities, as the content-defined chunking system can be integrated into various real-world scenarios where efficient data processing and management are paramount. The implications extend to data storage, data transmission, and beyond, promising to enhance the efficiency and performance of data processing systems [6]. This survey work contributes significantly to the field of hardware-accelerated data processing, offering a novel perspective on content-defined chunking and introducing innovative approaches that can benefit a variety of applications. By using non-hashing algorithms, harnessing FPGA technology, and embracing parallelism, the research not only addresses current challenges but also sets a foundation for future developments in this domain. In essence, this article underscores the importance of creative solutions and hardware acceleration in managing the ever-expanding world of data, setting the stage for further research and advancements in this critical area of data processing.

The research article titled "Accelerating ML/DL Applications with Hierarchical Caching on De-duplication Storage Clusters," authored by Prince Hamandawana, Awais Khan, Jongik Kim, and Tae-Sun Chung, presents an innovative approach to accelerate Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) applications through the implementation of hierarchical caching within de-duplication storage clusters [7]. A comprehensive review of the research: The survey begins by establishing the context and motivation behind the research. It elucidates the critical role of ML and DL in modern data analytics and the growing need for efficient data storage and retrieval systems that can support these applications. The motivation for accelerating ML and DL through hierarchical caching is emphasized, given their computationally intensive nature.

De-duplication Storage Clusters primarily focus on de-duplication storage clusters is explained. De-duplication is a data compression technique that eliminates redundant data, which can lead to significant storage and bandwidth savings. The survey outlines the advantages of de-duplication and its relevance in modern data management. The core concept of hierarchical caching is explored in detail. This caching strategy involves the use of multiple cache layers to optimize data access and retrieval. The survey investigates how hierarchical caching can enhance the performance of ML and DL applications by providing efficient and fast access to frequently used data. The central objective of the research, i.e., accelerating ML and DL applications, is analyzed. The survey assesses the impact of hierarchical caching on the speed and efficiency of these applications, leading to reduced latency and improved user experiences. The paper's technical implementation is scrutinized. The survey provides insights into how the researchers designed and implemented the hierarchical caching system within de-duplication storage clusters, including the architecture and algorithms used.

Figure.1 Deep Learning and Data De-Duplication transaction flow

The survey investigates the experimental results presented in the paper, focusing on performance metrics such as speed, latency, and resource utilization. It highlights the empirical evidence of the effectiveness of the proposed approach in accelerating ML and DL applications [8]. Practical implication of the research discusses the implementation of hierarchical caching in de-duplication storage clusters can be applied to real-world scenarios, benefiting data-intensive applications across various industries. The paper's contributions to the field of data management and ML/DL acceleration are evaluated. The survey underscores the significance of the research in terms of optimizing data access and retrieval for computationally intensive applications. The survey concludes by summarizing the key findings and contributions of the paper and suggests potential future research directions in the context of hierarchical caching, de-duplication, and ML/DL acceleration, offering insights into the evolving landscape of data storage and processing.

In this survey provides a comprehensive review of the research article "Accelerating ML/DL Applications with Hierarchical Caching on De-duplication Storage Clusters" published in the IEEE Transactions on Big Data. It explores the innovative use of hierarchical caching in de-duplication storage clusters and its significant impact on the acceleration of ML and DL applications, underscoring its importance in the context of modern data analytics and storage solutions. The research's contributions and potential applications are highlighted, offering a roadmap for future developments in this critical area of data management and acceleration [9].

III. ENSURING SECURE DATA MAINTENANCE

This survey offers a comprehensive analysis of the research paper titled "LOFS: A Lightweight Online File Storage Strategy for Effective Data De-duplication at Network Edge," authored by Geyao Cheng, Deke Guo, Lailong Luo, Junxu Xia, and Siyuan Gu, and published in IEEE Transactions on Parallel and Distributed Systems in 2021. The research investigates an innovative approach, "LOFS," designed to enhance data de-duplication at the network edge, with a specific focus on lightweight online file storage strategies. In the modern data landscape, efficient data de-duplication is of paramount importance, particularly at the network edge. This is a context characterized by resource limitations and the need for streamlined data management. The motivation behind this research stems from the increasing prominence of edge computing, which necessitates data de-duplication strategies tailored to optimize the use of storage space, reduce data transfer costs, and improve network bandwidth efficiency.

At the core of this research lies the "LOFS" strategy, which stands for "Lightweight Online File Storage." LOFS aims to address the unique challenges presented by network edge environments by providing a lightweight and online file storage strategy capable of effective data de-duplication. By being lightweight, LOFS ensures that resource-constrained edge devices can implement data de-duplication efficiently. Furthermore, the online nature of this strategy allows for real-time file storage, retrieval, and de-duplication, aligning with the dynamic demands of edge computing [10]. The central objective of the research is to enhance the effectiveness of data de-duplication at the network edge. This is achieved through the implementation of LOFS, resulting in reduced storage overhead, improved data transfer efficiency, and optimized network bandwidth usage. By developing a strategy that caters to the specific constraints and requirements of edge computing, the researchers aim to empower edge devices to perform data de-duplication effectively, ultimately contributing to the overall efficiency and performance of edge computing systems.

The technical implementation of LOFS is a critical aspect of the research. The survey investigates the architecture and algorithms employed in the LOFS strategy, shedding light on the mechanisms designed to ensure efficient data de-duplication. This technical insight provides a deeper understanding of how LOFS achieves its goals and how it can be applied in real-world edge computing scenarios [11]. The research's empirical validation is a noteworthy aspect, with the paper presenting experimental results and performance evaluations. These results demonstrate the effectiveness of the LOFS strategy by showcasing improved de-duplication ratios, storage efficiency, and data transfer speeds. This empirical evidence substantiates the claims of LOFS's effectiveness in optimizing data management at the network edge.

The practical implications of the LOFS strategy are explored in the survey. It discusses how the implementation of lightweight, online file storage strategies can be applied in various real-world edge computing applications and industries. The benefits of efficient data de-duplication, reduced storage costs, and improved network performance are highlighted as key takeaways from this research. In survey paper's contributions to the field of network edge computing and data de-duplication are noteworthy. The LOFS strategy presents an innovative approach to address the challenges of data management and optimization at the network edge. It offers a roadmap for future developments in the context of lightweight online file storage strategies, data de-duplication, and network edge

computing, ultimately contributing to the advancement of data management and optimization in edge computing environments [12].

This survey offers an in-depth analysis of the research paper "A Secure Privacy Preserving De-duplication Scheme for Cloud Computing," authored by Yongkai Fan, Xiaodong Lin, Wei Liang, Gang Tan, and Priyadarsi Nanda, addresses the pressing need for efficient data de-duplication in cloud computing, where vast amounts of data are managed, while simultaneously prioritizing data security and privacy [13]. The motivation for this research is rooted in the growing significance of preserving data confidentiality and safeguarding sensitive information in the cloud. Cloud computing and data de-duplication are closely intertwined, as data de-duplication is a crucial technique in the cloud to eliminate redundant data, reducing storage and bandwidth costs. However, the research highlights the emerging challenge of ensuring data privacy and security during de-duplication processes. The core concept of this study revolves around secure privacy-preserving de-duplication, emphasizing techniques and mechanisms that secure sensitive data and maintain confidentiality. It introduces novel privacy-preserving methods to ensure that data remains confidential while still benefiting from de-duplication [14].

In the context of cloud computing, data security and privacy are paramount, particularly in an era marked by stringent data protection regulations and an increasing focus on data breach prevention. This research contributes significantly to addressing these concerns, offering a strategy to ensure secure and private data handling in cloud computing environments. The technical implementation of the proposed scheme is a key focus, with the survey exploring the architectural design, cryptographic methods, and algorithms employed to create a secure and efficient de-duplication process.

The empirical validation of this research is another notable aspect, with the paper presenting experimental results that highlight the effectiveness of the proposed scheme [15]. These results demonstrate the efficient data de-duplication, data confidentiality, and computational overhead, reinforcing the feasibility of balancing data security and de-duplication efficiency. In practical terms, this research holds substantial implications, particularly in industries where data privacy and regulatory compliance are of paramount importance. In the field of cloud computing and data privacy are significant. It strikes a balance between data de-duplication's efficiency and data security and privacy requirements. The survey underscores the research's importance in addressing the complex challenges posed by data de-duplication in the cloud, offering a promising direction for future research and applications in data management and protection within cloud computing environments.

IV. CONCLUSION

In summary, the collective surveys of the research articles examined highlight the dynamic and ever-evolving landscape of deep learning and security in the field of computer science. From innovative data de-duplication techniques to secure privacy-preserving approaches in cloud computing, these studies collectively address the contemporary challenges and opportunities in the realm of data processing and storage systems. While each investigation focuses on distinct aspects of data management, they all share a common commitment to advancing the field. These surveys offer valuable insights, underscore the importance of security, privacy, and efficiency in data management, and provide a roadmap for future research directions in this ever-changing domain.

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